

The analytical data and relevant ir absorptions along with their assignments are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are yellow to red in colour, insensitive to atmospheric air and do not decompose when heated to their melting point. The analytical data show that stoichiometries correspond to the formula $SbX_2 \cdot L$ ($X=Cl$ or Br) or $SbCl_4 \cdot L$ indicating the presence of the ligands in their deprotonated form. The molar conductance ($3.1-8.3 \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene indicate the absence of ionic species and from the cryoscopic data for the complexes sufficiently soluble in nitrobenzene, it is concluded that they are monomeric and non-electrolytic, atleast, in solution.

The donor sites of the ligands have been identified on the basis of ir spectral data. The absence of characteristic absorptions attributable to the $\nu(NH)$ or $\nu(SH)$ in the spectra of the complexes indicates the deprotonation of the SH form of the bases (Ib) in presence of a Lewis acid. The deprotonation is enhanced due to the stabilization of the anion by conjugation with the >C=N-N=C< group⁸. Bonding through only one of the S atoms of the CSS group is inferred from the splitting of the strong $\nu_{as}(CSS)$ band^{9,10}. A band of medium to weak intensity appearing at $370 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the complexes of HL-1 (recorded upto 200 cm^{-1}) and being absent in the spectrum of the free Schiff base is tentatively assigned to the Sb-S stretching mode of vibration. The coordination through the N atom is indicated by the negative shift of $\nu(C=N)$ absorption frequency. The lowering is small, even negligible in a few cases, suggesting how little this mode of vibration is affected upon coordination¹¹. Bonding through both the N atoms is sterically not feasible and the involvement of the β -nitrogen in coordination is more likely as it gives rise to a five membered chelate ring with minimum strain.

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Preparation and Characterisation of Pyridine and 3-Picoline Adducts of Co(II) and Fe(II) Complexes

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IN continuation of our studies on metal complexes of different derivatives of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones^{1,2}, we report here the preparation and characterization of pyridine and 3-picoline adducts of Co(II) and Fe(II) complexes of 4-oximino-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OMPP), 4-oximino-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OMP), 4-oximino-3-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OPP) and 4-oximino-1,3-diphenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (ODPP).

Experimental

The chelating agents were prepared as described earlier². The hot ethanolic ligand solution containing 5 ml pyridine/3-picoline in slight excess over 1 : 2 metal : ligand ratio was added dropwise to the metal salt [$Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ or $FeSO_4 \cdot (NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$] solution in hot distilled water with constant stirring. The product was filtered, washed with cold water followed by ethanol and dried in air.

Metal content was estimated by titrating against standard EDTA solution after decomposing the complex. The thermograms of the compounds were recorded on 'Du Pont-950' thermogravimetric analyser. Other physico-chemical measurements were made as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) suggest 1 : 2 : 2 metal : ligand : base ratio in the complexes. The TGA studies gave the weight-loss (Table 1) of the compound and elimination temperature of the base and decomposition temperature of the compounds (Table 1).

The carbonyloximes are usually characterised by absorption due to C=O, C=N (oxime), N-O, O-H and C=N (cyclic) bonds. All ligands show strong and sharp band in the $1660-1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND TGA DATA

Compound	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)					Elimination temperature of pyridine/3-picoline °C	Decomposition temperature of complex °C
	Metal	Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen	Pyridine/3-picoline		
Co(OMPP) ₂ Py ₂	9.36 (9.48)	57.13 (57.93)	4.15 (4.22)	18.71 (18.08)	26.00 (25.45)	190	360
Co(OMP) ₂ Py ₂	12.48 (12.56)	45.49 (46.06)	4.02 (3.87)	24.02 (23.88)	34.00 (33.71)	230	310
Co(OPP) ₂ Py ₂	9.89 (9.93)	57.68 (56.67)	5.31 (5.10)	19.51 (18.88)	25.90 (26.66)	280	350
Co(ODPP) ₂ Py ₂	8.11 (7.90)	63.48 (64.42)	4.07 (4.60)	14.85 (15.03)	20.00 (21.22)	185	330
Co(OMPP) ₂ Pi ₂	9.02 (9.07)	60.32 (56.17)	4.13 (4.65)	17.15 (17.25)	28.00 (28.66)	180	350
Co(OMP) ₂ Pi ₂	11.43 (11.85)	49.19 (48.80)	4.55 (4.46)	22.19 (22.53)	36.00 (37.44)	220	310
Co(OPP) ₂ Pi ₂	9.23 (9.48)	58.89 (57.97)	4.96 (4.20)	18.48 (18.03)	30.20 (29.96)	350	340
Co(ODPP) ₂ Pi ₂	7.87 (7.62)	64.09 (65.20)	4.24 (4.43)	14.07 (14.48)	24.50 (24.06)	180	310
Fe(OMPP) ₂ Py ₂	9.02 (9.03)	58.13 (58.26)	4.40 (4.24)	18.30 (18.12)	25.50 (25.58)	180	260
Fe(OMP) ₂ Py ₂	12.00 (11.98)	46.06 (46.37)	3.88 (3.89)	24.19 (24.03)	—	—	210
Fe(OPP) ₂ Py ₂	10.01 (9.46)	57.48 (56.96)	4.46 (5.12)	19.27 (18.98)	—	—	230
Fe(ODPP) ₂ Py ₂	8.17 (7.52)	63.24 (64.70)	4.31 (4.61)	15.32 (15.09)	20.00 (21.30)	185	270
Fe(OMPP) ₂ Pi ₂	9.09 (8.64)	59.12 (59.45)	4.40 (4.68)	16.57 (17.33)	27.50 (28.80)	160	250
Fe(OMP) ₂ Pi ₂	11.09 (11.30)	47.63 (48.60)	4.21 (4.49)	22.18 (22.70)	—	—	205
Fe(OPP) ₂ Pi ₂	9.10 (9.03)	58.25 (58.26)	4.90 (4.22)	17.81 (18.12)	—	—	230
Fe(ODPP) ₂ Pi ₂	7.49 (7.25)	64.62 (65.46)	3.66 (4.45)	14.13 (14.54)	23.00 (24.16)	175	260

which may be assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ ³. Two bands of nearly equal intensity observed in the 1665-1590 cm^{-1} region might be due to $\nu_{C=N}$ (cyclic) and $\nu_{C=N}$ (oxime). The band at 1590 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ (oxime), while that at 1660 may be due to $\nu_{C=N}$ (cyclic). A strong and sharp band in the 1055-1030 cm^{-1} region may be assigned to ν_{N-O} ⁴. The higher ν_{N-O} suggests the presence of hydrogen bonding in the ligands⁵. A medium and strong band at 3200 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ν_{OH} . Low values of ν_{OH} confirm the presence of hydrogen bonding in the ligands⁶.

The vibrations of interest in pyridine and 3-picoline are $\nu_{C=C}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ bands between 1597-1429 cm^{-1} , C-H in plane deformation in the 1220-1053 cm^{-1} region, the ring breathing modes at 1053 and 1010 cm^{-1} and out of plane C-H deformation vibration near 405 cm^{-1} . All adducts show bands in the 1600-1430 cm^{-1} region which might be due to C=C and C=N symmetric and asymmetric vibrations⁷. A change of about 10 to 20 cm^{-1} in their band positions in adducts as compared to that of pyridine and 3-picoline is an indication of coordination of pyridine and 3-picoline to the metal ions⁸. The absence of ν_{OH} in all the adducts confirms deprotonation of oximino group on coordination. The lowering in $\nu_{C=O}$ is also mainly due to coordination through

oxygen of the carbonyl group. Higher ν_{N-O} , compared to its parent ligand, suggests coordination from nitrogen of the oximino group. The lowering of $\nu_{C=N}$ (oxime) supports coordination of nitrogen of the oximino group to the metal ion.

In diffuse reflectance spectrum of the adducts of Co(II) complexes, the three bands show splitting in two components indicating distortion from a regular octahedral structure⁹, which is supported by intensities of the bands. The tentative assignment for the observed transitions can be made as follows :

The diffuse reflectance spectra for the adducts of Fe(II) suggest the octahedral structure for the compounds. Each spectrum consists of broad asymmetric band ($\sim 12500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) with some structures and a low energy shoulder ($\sim 10000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The broad band may be assigned to ${}^6T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^6E_g$ transition which corresponds to $10 Dq$. The low energy shoulder might be due to low symmetry ligand field component, which lifts the two fold degeneracy of the 6E_g term¹⁰. The high energy band ($\sim 25000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) might be charge transfer in nature. It is required

that 10 Dq should be almost equal to the spin-pairing energy¹¹ $\pi = 2.5 B + 4 C \approx 18.5 B$ (assuming the usual relation $C \approx 4 B$). Thus taking $10 Dq = \pi$, B (600-780 cm⁻¹) is calculated. The nephelauxetic ratio β (0.6-0.7) indicates reduction in B upon coordination, which suggests the partial covalent nature of the M-L bond¹².

The observed magnetic moments of the Co(II) adducts are in the 3.56-4.85 B.M. range. The low value of Co(OMPP)₂Py₂ (3.75 B.M.) and Co(OMPP)₂Pi₂ (3.56 B.M.) may be due to factors discussed by Stoufer *et al*¹³. The magnetic moments of other Co(II) adducts are very close to six coordinate octahedral structure. The lower magnetic moments of the Fe(II) adducts can be attributed to the trigonal distortion of the compounds¹³. This distortion allows the excited ⁵E_g term to be mixed into the ground term by both the crystal field and spin-orbit coupling.

In view of these, the following octahedral structure for all the adducts may be suggested.

R = H or CH₃, R₁ = H or C₆H₅, R₂ = CH₃ or C₆H₅.

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Co(III) and Fe(III) Chelates of N,N'-Hexamethylene-bis-(2,5-di-OH-Acetophenone/Propiophenone/Benzophenone)†

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CHELATION properties of the Schiff bases derived from hexamethylenediamine and 2,5-di-OH-acetophenone/propiophenone/benzophenone have been studied earlier¹. The present communication deals with the synthesis and characterization of the title complexes.

Experimental

The Schiff bases, N,N'-hexamethylene-bis-(2,5-di-OH-acetophenone / propiophenone / benzophenone), were prepared by the reported method¹. Co(III) complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolecular mixture of CoCl₂ and the Schiff base. Hydrogen peroxide was used for the oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III). The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained at 6.5-7 by sodium acetate buffer. Fe(III) complexes were similarly prepared from FeCl₃ and in the absence of hydrogen peroxide. The greenish-yellow and reddish-brown precipitates of Co(III) and Fe(III) complexes respectively were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and finally dried over fused CaCl₂ in a vacuum desiccator.

Physical measurements were carried out by methods reported earlier^{1,2}. Chlorine was estimated by Haywood-Kay method³.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) show 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) composition. The low molar conductance values of the complexes are ascribed to their non-electrolytic nature. The endothermic peaks observed at 122-134° in the DTA curve (Fig. 1) suggest the presence of coordinated water molecule. The TGA studies (Fig. 2) reveal that the percent weight loss upto 126-142° for the complexes corresponds to the loss of one water molecule suggesting a general formula MSB(H₂O)Cl. The complete decomposition takes place at 680-720° leaving behind metal oxides.

The band at 3240-3200 cm⁻¹ in the ligands assignable to νOH mode is retained in the complexes

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